

Classification of derived Azumaya Algebras over derived smooth manifolds via derived Brauer Groups

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Abstract

For a derived smooth manifold (X, \mathcal{O}_X) in the sense of Spivak, we pull back Toën’s categorical derived Brauer stack along the forgetful functor from simplicial C^∞ -rings to connective simplicial commutative rings and then stackify on the open site of X . The resulting categorical Brauer stack has the homotopy type

$$\mathfrak{Br}_X \simeq K(\mathbb{Z}, 1) \times B^2GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X).$$

Consequently its group of stackified Brauer classes is

$$dBr(X) := \pi_0\Gamma(X, \mathfrak{Br}_X) \cong H^1(X, \mathbb{Z}) \times \pi_0\Gamma(X, B^2GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)),$$

where $GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)$ is the sheaf of derived units. The usual formula with $H^2(X, \mathcal{O}_X^\times)$ is recovered when the structure sheaf is discrete. This shows that the pullback categorical Brauer invariant is governed by the full homotopy type of the derived unit sheaf.

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1 Introduction

The theory of Azumaya algebras is a bridge between algebra, geometry, and cohomology. Besides their central role in algebraic geometry, Azumaya algebras also arise naturally in differential geometry and mathematical physics, where they are closely related to bundle gerbes, twisted vector bundles, and D -branes in backgrounds with nontrivial B -fields. In particular, Schweigert, Tropp, and Valentino established a Serre–Swan correspondence identifying the category of gerbe modules with the category of finitely generated projective modules over an associated Azumaya algebra on compact smooth manifolds and, more generally, on étale Lie groupoids [Schweigert–Tropp–Valentino]. Classically, Azumaya algebras over a commutative ring or a scheme are classified up to Morita equivalence by the Brauer group, which is closely related to cohomology with coefficients in the sheaf of units.

Toën extended this picture to derived algebraic geometry. For a derived stack F , he constructed a categorical Brauer object whose homotopy type is governed by

$$K(\mathbb{Z}, 1) \quad \text{and} \quad K(\mathbb{G}_m, 2).$$

The purpose of this paper is to transport the categorical part of Toën’s theory to derived smooth manifolds in the sense of Spivak. A derived smooth manifold (X, \mathcal{O}_X) carries a sheaf of simplicial C^∞ -rings rather than a sheaf of simplicial commutative rings. Since every simplicial C^∞ -ring has an underlying connective simplicial commutative \mathbb{R} -algebra, the forgetful functor allows us to evaluate Toën’s derived Brauer stack on

$$U \longmapsto \mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\text{alg}},$$

where $U \subset X$ is open. Because the ordinary open-cover topology on X differs from the fppf and étale topologies appearing in Toën’s construction, the resulting objectwise prestack is not expected to satisfy descent. We therefore define the categorical smooth Brauer stack by stackifying this prestack on the ordinary open site of X .

Throughout the paper, the phrase “derived Azumaya algebra over a simplicial C^∞ -ring” is understood in this transported sense: namely, a derived Azumaya algebra over the underlying simplicial commutative ring A^{alg} . We do not construct an intrinsic Morita theory of derived C^∞ -Azumaya algebras; developing such a theory would constitute a separate and substantially deeper project.

Our main result is the following classification of stackified Brauer classes:

$$dBr(X) := \pi_0\Gamma(X, \mathfrak{B}\mathfrak{r}_X) \cong H^1(X, \mathbb{Z}) \times \pi_0\Gamma(X, B^2GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)).$$

Here $GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)$ denotes the sheaf of derived units of the structure sheaf. Consequently, after pullback to the smooth site, the role played by \mathbb{G}_m in Toën’s algebraic theory is replaced by the full derived unit sheaf. In particular, when \mathcal{O}_X is genuinely derived, $GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)$ is a sheaf of grouplike spaces rather than merely the discrete sheaf $(\pi_0\mathcal{O}_X)^\times$. Thus the pullback categorical Brauer invariant is governed by the full homotopy type of the derived unit sheaf.

Finally, we compare the above classification with familiar cohomological invariants. Since our construction is carried out entirely at the level of sheaves, the comparison depends only on the

choice of coefficient sheaf rather than on the definition of derived smooth manifolds themselves. When the structure sheaf is discrete,

$$GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X) = \mathcal{O}_X^\times,$$

and the second factor reduces to

$$H^2(X, \mathcal{O}_X^\times).$$

For an ordinary smooth manifold (M, C_M^∞) with real-valued smooth functions, the sheaf of positive units is soft, and therefore

$$H^2(M, (C_M^\infty)^\times) \cong H^2(M, \mathbb{Z}_2).$$

Consequently,

$$dBr(M) \cong H^1(M, \mathbb{Z}) \times H^2(M, \mathbb{Z}_2).$$

The same sheaf-theoretic argument also applies to the coefficient sheaf of complex-valued smooth functions. Replacing $(C_M^\infty)^\times$ by $C_M^\infty(\mathbb{C})^\times$, the exponential sequence yields

$$H^2(M, C_M^\infty(\mathbb{C})^\times) \cong H^3(M, \mathbb{Z}),$$

recovering the classical Dixmier–Douady class. This comparison reflects only the choice of coefficient sheaf and should not be interpreted as replacing Spivak’s real-valued derived smooth manifolds by a complex analogue. Thus the pullback categorical Brauer invariant should be regarded as a new smooth invariant rather than a replacement for existing topological Brauer groups.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 recalls simplicial C^∞ -rings, Spivak’s derived smooth manifolds, and the necessary background from higher category theory. Section 3 transports Toën’s Brauer theory along the forgetful functor to simplicial commutative rings. Section 4 constructs the pullback categorical Brauer stack and computes its homotopy type. Section 5 proves the classification theorem and discusses the natural injection from representable derived Azumaya classes into the categorical Brauer invariant. Finally, Section 6 recovers the discrete and ordinary smooth cohomological formulas.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Simplicial commutative rings and simplicial C^∞ -rings

We recall two algebraic frameworks that appear in derived algebraic geometry and derived differential geometry, respectively.

Definition 2.1 (Simplicial commutative ring, [Mathew]). *A simplicial commutative ring is a simplicial object in the category of commutative rings, i.e. a functor*

$$A : \Delta^{\text{op}} \longrightarrow \mathbf{CR},$$

where Δ is the simplex category. Morphisms are natural transformations. The category of simplicial commutative rings is denoted by $s\mathbf{CR}$.

Definition 2.2 (Lax simplicial C^∞ -ring, [Spivak]). A lax simplicial C^∞ -ring is a fibrant object in the model category obtained by localizing the functor category $\mathbf{sSets}^{\mathbb{E}}$ at the maps

$$p_{i,j} : H_{\mathbb{R}^{i+j}} \longrightarrow H_{\mathbb{R}^i} \amalg H_{\mathbb{R}^j},$$

where \mathbb{E} is the category of Euclidean spaces and smooth maps. Equivalently, a lax simplicial C^∞ -ring is a functor $F : \mathbb{E} \longrightarrow \mathbf{sSets}$, such that $F(\mathbb{R}^n)$ is a Kan complex for all n , and for all $i, j \in \mathbb{N}$, the natural map

$$F(\mathbb{R}^{i+j}) \longrightarrow F(\mathbb{R}^i) \times F(\mathbb{R}^j)$$

is a weak equivalence.

Morphisms are natural transformations. The category of lax simplicial C^∞ -rings is denoted by $\mathbf{lax} - s\mathbf{C}^\infty$.

Remark 2.3. There is also a model category of strict simplicial C^∞ -rings, consisting of (strictly) product preserving functors from \mathbb{E} to \mathbf{sSets} . This model category is Quillen equivalent to the model category $\mathbf{lax} - s\mathbf{C}^\infty$ of lax simplicial C^∞ -rings (see [Spivak, 5.2] and [Lurie-DAG I, 15.3]).

Definition 2.4. A simplicial C^∞ -ring is a simplicial object in the category of C^∞ -rings, i.e. a functor

$$F : \Delta^{\text{op}} \longrightarrow \mathbf{C}^\infty.$$

where Δ is the simplex category. Morphisms are natural transformations. The category of simplicial C^∞ rings is denoted by $s\mathbf{C}^\infty$.

2.2 The equivalence of two definitions via Lawvere theory

Proposition 2.5. There is an equivalence of categories

$$\mathbf{Fun}^\times(\mathbb{E}, \mathbf{sSets}) \simeq s\mathbf{C}^\infty,$$

where $\mathbf{Fun}^\times(\mathbb{E}, \mathbf{sSets})$ denotes the category of product-preserving functors from \mathbb{E} to simplicial sets. In particular, the strict simplicial C^∞ -rings described in Remark 2.3 are equivalent to the simplicial C^∞ -rings in Definition 2.4.

Proof. It is well known that the category of C^∞ -rings is equivalent to the category of product-preserving functors $\mathbf{C}^\infty \simeq \mathbf{Fun}^\times(\mathbb{E}, \mathbf{Set})$ ([Joyce], Example 2.3. and Definition 2.4.), where \mathbb{E} is the category of Euclidean spaces and smooth maps. Explicitly, a C^∞ -ring A corresponds to the functor $\mathbb{R}^n \longmapsto \text{Hom}_{\mathbf{C}^\infty}(C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n), A)$, and this defines an equivalence of categories. Here $C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n)$ is the free C^∞ -ring on n generators.

Passing to simplicial objects, this equivalence induces an equivalence

$$s\mathbf{C}^\infty \simeq \mathbf{Fun}^\times(\mathbb{E}, \mathbf{sSets}),$$

which we now describe explicitly.

Let $A_\bullet : \Delta^{\text{op}} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}^\infty$ be a simplicial C^∞ -ring. Define a functor

$$\Phi(A_\bullet) : \mathbb{E} \rightarrow \mathbf{sSets}$$

by

$$\Phi(A_\bullet)(\mathbb{R}^n)_k := \text{Hom}_{\mathbf{C}^\infty}(C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^n), A_k).$$

We claim that $\Phi(A_\bullet)$ preserves finite products strictly. For each simplicial degree k , using the universal property of the free C^∞ -ring, one has a chain of natural isomorphisms

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(A_\bullet)(\mathbb{R}^{i+j})_k &= \text{Hom}_{\mathbf{C}^\infty}(C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^{i+j}), A_k) \\ &\cong A_k^{i+j} \\ &\cong A_k^i \times A_k^j \\ &\cong \text{Hom}_{\mathbf{C}^\infty}(C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^i), A_k) \times \text{Hom}_{\mathbf{C}^\infty}(C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^j), A_k) \\ &\cong \Phi(A_\bullet)(\mathbb{R}^i)_k \times \Phi(A_\bullet)(\mathbb{R}^j)_k. \end{aligned}$$

These isomorphisms are natural in k and compatible with the simplicial structure maps, hence assemble to an isomorphism of simplicial sets

$$\Phi(A_\bullet)(\mathbb{R}^{i+j}) \cong \Phi(A_\bullet)(\mathbb{R}^i) \times \Phi(A_\bullet)(\mathbb{R}^j).$$

Conversely, let $F : \mathbb{E} \rightarrow \mathbf{sSets}$ be a product-preserving functor. Since limits in \mathbf{sSets} are computed levelwise, for each simplicial degree k , the functor $F_k : \mathbb{E} \rightarrow \mathbf{Set}$ preserves finite products, and hence corresponds to a C^∞ -ring. Denote this ring by $\Psi(F)_k$. The simplicial structure maps of F induce morphisms of C^∞ -rings, and therefore define a simplicial object $\Psi(F) : \Delta^{\text{op}} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}^\infty$.

Finally, these constructions are inverse to each other up to natural isomorphism. Indeed, for A_\bullet , one has $\Psi(\Phi(A_\bullet))_k \cong A_k$, by the universal property of free C^∞ -rings, and for F , one has $\Phi(\Psi(F))(\mathbb{R}^n)_k \cong F_k(\mathbb{R}^n)$, naturally in n and k . This shows that the two constructions are mutually inverse, and hence establishes the equivalence. \square

2.3 Derived manifolds

Definition 2.6 (Affine derived manifold, [Spivak]). *An affine derived manifold is a pair $\mathcal{X} = (X, \mathcal{O}_X) \in \mathbf{LRS}$, where $\mathcal{O}_X \in s\mathbf{C}^\infty$ is fibrant, and which can be obtained as the homotopy limit in a diagram of the form*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \mathcal{X} & \longrightarrow & \mathbb{R}^0 \\ \downarrow g & & \downarrow 0 \\ \mathbb{R}^n & \xrightarrow{f} & \mathbb{R}^k \end{array}$$

Recall that \mathbf{LRS} denotes the simplicial category of local C^∞ -ringed spaces (see Definition 6.3) [Spivak]. We sometimes refer to an affine derived manifold as a *local model* for derived manifolds. The map $\mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is called the *canonical inclusion of the zero set*.

Definition 2.7 (Derived smooth manifold, [Spivak]). *A derived smooth manifold (or derived manifold) is a local C^∞ -ringed space $(X, \mathcal{O}_X) \in \mathbf{LRS}$, where $\mathcal{O}_X \in s\mathbf{C}^\infty$ is fibrant, and for which there exists an open covering $\bigcup_i U_i = X$ such that each $(U_i, \mathcal{O}_X|_{U_i})$ is an affine derived manifold.*

2.4 Modules over simplicial C^∞ -rings

Before introducing differential graded models, we first recall the notion of a module over a simplicial C^∞ -ring [Steffens]. Let

$$sC^\infty\text{ring} := \text{Fun}^\pi(\text{CartSp}, \mathcal{S})$$

be the ∞ -category of product-preserving functors; its objects are called *simplicial C^∞ -rings*. Every $A \in sC^\infty\text{ring}$ has an *underlying simplicial commutative \mathbb{R} -algebra* denoted A^{alg} . Indeed, the inclusion

$$\text{Poly}_{\mathbb{R}} \hookrightarrow \text{CartSp}$$

induces a forgetful functor $(_)^{\text{alg}} : sC^\infty\text{ring} \rightarrow \text{CAlg}_{\mathbb{R}}^{\geq 0}$, which is conservative and preserves limits and colimits. Here $\text{CAlg}_{\mathbb{R}}^{\geq 0}$ denotes the ∞ -category of connective \mathbb{E}_∞ -algebras over \mathbb{R} (equivalently, connective simplicial commutative \mathbb{R} -algebras).

Definition 2.8 ([Steffens]). *Let Mod^\otimes be the ∞ -category of MComm^\otimes -algebras in $\text{Mod}_{\mathbb{R}}$ (i.e. the ∞ -operad governing \mathbb{E}_∞ -algebras and modules over them). We define the ∞ -category Mod as the pullback*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{Mod} & \longrightarrow & \text{Alg}_{\text{MComm}}(\text{Mod}_{\mathbb{R}}) \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ sC^\infty\text{ring} & \longrightarrow & \text{CAlg}_{\mathbb{R}}^{\geq 0} \end{array}$$

where the lower horizontal arrow is $(_)^{\text{alg}}$. An object $(A, M) \in \text{Mod}$ consists of a simplicial C^∞ -ring A and an A^{alg} -module M . For a fixed A , we denote by Mod_A the fibre over A ; it is the ∞ -category of A -modules.

2.5 Differential graded models

We now turn to *differential graded models* for simplicial C^∞ -rings. These models give an explicit algebraic presentation that is particularly convenient for geometry, for example for differential graded manifolds.

Theorem 2.9 (C^∞ -Dold–Kan correspondence, [Steffens]). *There is a canonical equivalence of ∞ -categories*

$$sC^\infty\text{ring} \simeq C^\infty\text{Alg}^{\geq 0},$$

where $C^\infty\text{Alg}^{\geq 0}$ is the ∞ -category obtained from $C^\infty\text{dga}^{\geq 0}$ by inverting the weak equivalences. In particular, every simplicial C^∞ -ring can be represented by a C^∞ -differential graded algebra.

2.6 Left exact localizations

We recall the basic facts on left exact localizations that will be used throughout the paper. Standard references are [Lurie-HTT, §6.2].

Definition 2.10. *Let \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{D} be ∞ -categories admitting finite limits. A functor $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ is called left exact if it preserves all finite limits.*

The following standard criterion will be used repeatedly.

Lemma 2.11. *For a functor $F : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ between finitely complete ∞ -categories, the following are equivalent.*

1. F is left exact.
2. F preserves pullbacks and terminal objects.
3. F preserves binary products and equalizers.

Proof. This is the standard characterization of finite-limit-preserving functors; see, for example, [Borceux, Proposition 2.8.2]. \square

The stackification functor is the principal example of a left exact localization.

Lemma 2.12. *Let X be a topological space and let*

$$L : \mathrm{PSh}(X, \mathcal{S}) \longrightarrow \mathrm{Sh}(X, \mathcal{S})$$

be the stackification functor. Then L is an accessible left exact localization.

Proof. By [Lurie-HTT, Lemma 6.2.2.7], $\mathrm{Sh}(X, \mathcal{S})$ is a topological localization of $\mathrm{PSh}(X, \mathcal{S})$. Every topological localization is accessible and left exact by [Lurie-HTT, Corollary 6.2.1.7]. \square

As a consequence, stackification preserves all finite limits. In particular, it preserves terminal objects, products, pullbacks, equalizers, group objects, and all constructions defined by finite limits. These properties will be used repeatedly without further mention.

3 The Automorphism Computation

The key input in Toën’s theory of derived Azumaya algebras is that the trivial locally presentable dg-category has no unexpected higher auto-equivalences. More precisely, Toën proves that all self-equivalences are generated by integer shifts and tensoring with invertible modules. This fact is the starting point for the classification of derived Brauer classes.

In the smooth derived setting, we transport this computation objectwise by means of the forgetful functor from simplicial C^∞ -rings to simplicial commutative \mathbb{R} -algebras.

3.1 The forgetful functor

Recall from Section 2 that there exists a canonical forgetful functor

$$(-)^{\mathrm{alg}} : sC^\infty \mathrm{ring} \longrightarrow s\mathbf{CR}_{\mathbb{R}}$$

which sends a simplicial C^∞ -ring to its underlying connective simplicial commutative \mathbb{R} -algebra. Therefore, for every derived smooth manifold (X, \mathcal{O}_X) and every open subset $U \subset X$, the object $\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\mathrm{alg}}$ is a connective simplicial commutative ring, so Toën’s derived Azumaya theory applies objectwise.

3.2 Transporting Toën's theory to the smooth setting

Recall that Toën defines a derived substack

$$\mathbb{D}g^{Az} \subset I(\mathbb{D}g^{lp, desc})$$

whose objects are dg-categories locally equivalent, for the fppf topology, to the dg-category associated to a derived Azumaya algebra [Toën, §2.2]. By Proposition 1.14 and Corollary 2.12 of [Toën], every derived Azumaya algebra is locally Morita equivalent to the trivial dg-category. Consequently, one has a natural equivalence of derived stacks $\mathbb{D}g^{Az} \simeq K(\mathbb{Z}, 1) \times K(\mathbb{G}_m, 2)$.

Since every simplicial commutative \mathbb{R} -algebra is canonically a simplicial commutative \mathbb{Z} -algebra, the derived stack $\mathbb{D}g^{Az}$ restricts naturally to simplicial commutative \mathbb{R} -algebras. To transport this construction to derived smooth geometry, we use the canonical forgetful functor

$$(-)^{\text{alg}} : sC^\infty\text{Ring} \longrightarrow s\mathbf{CR}_{\mathbb{R}},$$

which sends a simplicial C^∞ -ring to its underlying simplicial commutative \mathbb{R} -algebra.

Definition 3.1. *Let (X, \mathcal{O}_X) be a derived smooth manifold. For every open subset $U \subset X$, define the derived Brauer space of U by*

$$\mathfrak{B}\mathfrak{r}_X^{\text{pre}}(U) := \mathbb{D}g^{Az}(\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\text{alg}}),$$

where $\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\text{alg}}$ denotes the underlying simplicial commutative \mathbb{R} -algebra of the simplicial C^∞ -ring $\mathcal{O}_X(U)$.

The construction is summarized by the diagram

$$\text{Open}(X) \xrightarrow{\mathcal{O}_X^{\text{op}}} sC^\infty\text{Ring}^{\text{op}} \xrightarrow{(-)^{\text{alg}, \text{op}}} s\mathbf{CR}_{\mathbb{R}}^{\text{op}} \hookrightarrow s\mathbb{Z}\text{-CAlg}^{\text{op}},$$

followed by evaluation of the derived stack $\mathbb{D}g^{Az}$. Equivalently, for every open subset $U \subset X$, we first form the underlying simplicial commutative ring $\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\text{alg}}$, and then evaluate Toën's derived stack on this object. Since $\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\text{alg}}$ is connective for every open subset $U \subset X$, Toën's local triviality theorem applies objectwise. Therefore no additional local triviality argument is required in the derived smooth setting.

4 The Smooth Derived Brauer Stack

4.1 Two topologies

Toën's derived Brauer stack is defined on simplicial commutative rings and satisfies descent for the étale or fppf topology. A derived smooth manifold (X, \mathcal{O}_X) , on the other hand, is equipped with the open-cover topology on its underlying topological space X .

For an open inclusion $V \subset U$, the restriction morphism $\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\text{alg}} \longrightarrow \mathcal{O}_X(V)^{\text{alg}}$ is generally not an étale morphism in the sense relevant to Toën's theorem. Consequently, étale descent for $\mathbb{D}g^{Az}$ does not by itself imply open-cover descent for the presheaf obtained by evaluating $\mathbb{D}g^{Az}$ on the rings $\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\text{alg}}$. For this reason, the object we ultimately want is the stackification of the resulting prestack on the open site of X .

4.2 Presheaves in the ∞ -categorical sense

We briefly clarify the sense in which the Brauer prestack below is a presheaf. Let (X, \mathcal{O}_X) be a derived smooth manifold. Its structure sheaf is regarded as a sheaf of simplicial C^∞ -rings on the ordinary open site of X ; equivalently, it determines an object

$$\mathcal{O}_X \in \mathrm{Sh}(X, sC^\infty\mathrm{Ring}).$$

After applying the forgetful functor

$$(-)^{\mathrm{alg}} : sC^\infty\mathrm{Ring} \longrightarrow s\mathbb{Z}\text{-}\mathrm{CAlg},$$

we obtain a sheaf of connective simplicial commutative rings

$$\mathcal{O}_X^{\mathrm{alg}} \in \mathrm{Sh}(X, s\mathbb{Z}\text{-}\mathrm{CAlg}).$$

In particular, by evaluation on open subsets, this gives a functor

$$\mathrm{Open}(X)^{op} \longrightarrow s\mathbb{Z}\text{-}\mathrm{CAlg}, \quad U \longmapsto \mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\mathrm{alg}}.$$

Composing this functor with Toën's Brauer functor

$$\mathbb{D}g^{Az} : s\mathbb{Z}\text{-}\mathrm{CAlg} \longrightarrow \mathcal{S}$$

gives an object

$$\mathfrak{Br}_X^{\mathrm{pre}} \in \mathrm{PSh}(X, \mathcal{S}) = \mathrm{Fun}(\mathrm{Open}(X)^{op}, \mathcal{S}).$$

Thus the assignment

$$U \longmapsto \mathbb{D}g^{Az}(\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\mathrm{alg}})$$

is a presheaf of spaces in the ∞ -categorical sense.

If one chooses a strict fibrant model for the structure sheaf, the same presheaf may be represented by a homotopy-coherent restriction diagram on open subsets. Different choices of model give equivalent objects of $\mathrm{PSh}(X, \mathcal{S})$. Therefore the stackification

$$\mathfrak{Br}_X := \mathrm{St}(\mathfrak{Br}_X^{\mathrm{pre}})$$

does not depend on any strictification choice.

4.3 Construction of the Brauer stack

Recall that, for every connective simplicial commutative ring A , Toën associates a derived stack

$$\mathbb{D}g^{Az}(A)$$

classifying derived Azumaya dg-categories over A , up to Morita equivalence [Toën, §2.2].

Let (X, \mathcal{O}_X) be a derived smooth manifold. Evaluating Toën's construction on the underlying simplicial commutative rings $\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\mathrm{alg}}$, $U \subset X$, defines a prestack on the open site of X .

Definition 4.1. For every open subset $U \subset X$, define

$$\mathfrak{B}\mathfrak{r}_X^{\text{pre}}(U) := \mathbb{D}g^{\text{Az}}(\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\text{alg}}).$$

The assignment $U \mapsto \mathfrak{B}\mathfrak{r}_X^{\text{pre}}(U)$ is called the Brauer prestack of X . The smooth derived Brauer stack of X is defined to be the stackification

$$\mathfrak{B}\mathfrak{r}_X := \text{St}(\mathfrak{B}\mathfrak{r}_X^{\text{pre}})$$

with respect to the open-cover topology on X .

Remark 4.2. We emphasize that, in general, one should not expect $\mathfrak{B}\mathfrak{r}_X^{\text{pre}} \simeq \mathfrak{B}\mathfrak{r}_X$. Indeed, Toën's derived stack $\mathbb{D}g^{\text{Az}}$ satisfies descent for the étale (equivalently, fppf) topology on simplicial commutative rings, whereas the site $\text{Open}(X)$ carries the ordinary open-cover topology. Therefore the objectwise pullback prestack need not satisfy descent on $\text{Open}(X)$, and stackification is required.

4.4 Delooping and stackification

Lemma 4.3. Let

$$L : \text{PSh}(X, \mathcal{S}) \longrightarrow \text{Sh}(X, \mathcal{S})$$

denote the stackification functor. For every sheaf of grouplike spaces $G \in \text{Sh}(X, \mathcal{S})$, the stackification of the presheaf $U \mapsto B^2(G(U))$ is canonically equivalent to the internal double delooping B^2G in the ∞ -topos $\text{Sh}(X, \mathcal{S})$.

Proof. By [Lurie-HTT, Lem. 6.2.2.7], the category $\text{Sh}(X, \mathcal{S})$ is a topological localization of $\text{PSh}(X, \mathcal{S})$. Moreover, every topological localization is left exact [Lurie-HTT, Cor. 6.2.1.7]. Hence the stackification functor

$$L : \text{PSh}(X, \mathcal{S}) \longrightarrow \text{Sh}(X, \mathcal{S})$$

preserves finite limits. Let H be a grouplike presheaf of spaces. Since L preserves finite limits, it preserves loop objects, and therefore

$$\Omega(L(BH)) \simeq L(\Omega BH) \simeq L(H).$$

Hence $L(BH)$ is a classifying object for $L(H)$. Classifying objects are unique in any ∞ -topos [Lurie-HTT, §7.2.2]. Therefore there is a canonical equivalence

$$L(BH) \simeq B(LH).$$

Applying this first with $H = G$ and then with $H = BG$ yields

$$L(B^2G) \simeq B^2(LG).$$

Since G is already a sheaf,

$$L(G) \simeq G,$$

and consequently $L(B^2G) \simeq B^2G$. Equivalently, the objectwise presheaf $U \mapsto B^2(G(U))$ stackifies to the internal double delooping B^2G . \square

Lemma 4.4. *The stackification of the constant presheaf*

$$U \mapsto K(\mathbb{Z}, 1)$$

is canonically equivalent to $K(\underline{\mathbb{Z}}, 1)$, where $\underline{\mathbb{Z}}$ denotes the constant sheaf with value \mathbb{Z} .

Proof. The constant presheaf with value \mathbb{Z} sheafifies to the constant sheaf $\underline{\mathbb{Z}}$. By [Lurie-HTT, Lem. 6.2.2.7], $\mathrm{Sh}(X, \mathcal{S})$ is a topological localization of $\mathrm{PSh}(X, \mathcal{S})$, and by [Lurie-HTT, Cor. 6.2.1.7] the associated stackification functor is left exact.

Left exact functors preserve group objects. Since Eilenberg–MacLane objects in an ∞ -topos are determined by the corresponding group objects [Lurie-HTT, §7.2.2], the stackification of

$$U \mapsto K(\mathbb{Z}, 1)$$

is precisely the Eilenberg–MacLane object associated to the sheaf $\underline{\mathbb{Z}}$, namely

$$K(\underline{\mathbb{Z}}, 1).$$

□

Theorem 4.5. *Let (X, \mathcal{O}_X) be a derived smooth manifold. There is a natural equivalence of stacks on X*

$$\mathfrak{Bt}_X \simeq K(\underline{\mathbb{Z}}, 1) \times B^2(GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)).$$

Proof. For every open subset $U \subset X$, the simplicial commutative ring $\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\mathrm{alg}}$ is connective. Hence Toën’s theorem applies objectwise and yields [Toën, Cor. 2.12]

$$\mathbb{D}g^{Az}(\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\mathrm{alg}}) \simeq K(\mathbb{Z}, 1) \times K(\mathbb{G}_m, 2)$$

Evaluating the second factor on $\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\mathrm{alg}}$ and using $\mathbb{G}_m(\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\mathrm{alg}}) = GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X(U)^{\mathrm{alg}})$, we obtain

$$\mathfrak{Bt}_X^{\mathrm{pre}}(U) \simeq K(\mathbb{Z}, 1) \times B^2GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X(U)).$$

These equivalences are functorial in U , and therefore assemble to an equivalence of prestacks

$$\mathfrak{Bt}_X^{\mathrm{pre}} \simeq K(\mathbb{Z}, 1)^{\mathrm{pre}} \times B^2(GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X))^{\mathrm{pre}}.$$

By [Lurie-HTT, Lem. 6.2.2.7], stackification is a topological localization, and by [Lurie-HTT, Cor. 6.2.1.7] it is left exact. Hence, by Lemma 2.11, stackification preserves finite products, so

$$\mathfrak{Bt}_X = \mathrm{St}(\mathfrak{Bt}_X^{\mathrm{pre}}) \simeq \mathrm{St}(K(\mathbb{Z}, 1)^{\mathrm{pre}}) \times \mathrm{St}(B^2(GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X))^{\mathrm{pre}}).$$

By Lemmas 4.4 and 4.3, $\mathrm{St}(K(\mathbb{Z}, 1)^{\mathrm{pre}}) \simeq K(\underline{\mathbb{Z}}, 1)$ and

$$\mathrm{St}(B^2(GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X))^{\mathrm{pre}}) \simeq B^2(GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)).$$

Therefore

$$\mathfrak{Bt}_X \simeq K(\underline{\mathbb{Z}}, 1) \times B^2(GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)).$$

□

Corollary 4.6. *The higher homotopical structure of the smooth derived Brauer stack is completely determined by the sheaf of units $GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)$ together with the discrete factor $K(\underline{\mathbb{Z}}, 1)$. Equivalently, all higher Brauer-theoretic information in the derived smooth setting is encoded in the Postnikov tower of $GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)$.*

5 Classification of Smooth Derived Brauer Classes

Definition 5.1. *Let (X, \mathcal{O}_X) be a derived smooth manifold. The smooth derived Brauer group of X is defined by*

$$dBr(X) := \pi_0 \Gamma(X, \mathfrak{B}r_X) = \pi_0 \text{Map}_{\text{Sh}(X, \mathcal{S})}(1, \mathfrak{B}r_X).$$

Since the smooth derived Brauer stack $\mathfrak{B}r_X$ is a grouplike object in the ∞ -topos $\text{Sh}(X, \mathcal{S})$, the set $dBr(X)$ inherits a natural abelian group structure. Under the equivalence of Theorem 4.5,

$$\mathfrak{B}r_X \simeq K(\mathbb{Z}, 1) \times B^2GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X),$$

this group law corresponds to the product structure on the two factors.

Theorem 5.2 (Classification theorem). *Let (X, \mathcal{O}_X) be a derived smooth manifold. There is a natural isomorphism*

$$dBr(X) \cong H^1(X, \mathbb{Z}) \times \pi_0 \Gamma(X, B^2GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)).$$

Proof. By Theorem 4.5, there is a natural equivalence

$$\mathfrak{B}r_X \simeq K(\mathbb{Z}, 1) \times B^2GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X).$$

Recall that $\Gamma(X, -) = \text{Map}_{\text{Sh}(X, \mathcal{S})}(1, -)$ is represented by the terminal object of the ∞ -topos $\text{Sh}(X, \mathcal{S})$. Hence it preserves finite products. Therefore

$$\Gamma(X, \mathfrak{B}r_X) \simeq \Gamma(X, K(\mathbb{Z}, 1)) \times \Gamma(X, B^2GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)).$$

Passing to connected components yields

$$dBr(X) = \pi_0 \Gamma(X, \mathfrak{B}r_X) \simeq \pi_0 \Gamma(X, K(\mathbb{Z}, 1)) \times \pi_0 \Gamma(X, B^2GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)).$$

The first factor is identified with sheaf cohomology by the general theory of Eilenberg–MacLane objects in an ∞ -topos [Lurie-HTT, §7.2.2]:

$$\pi_0 \Gamma(X, K(\mathbb{Z}, 1)) \cong H^1(X, \mathbb{Z}).$$

Consequently,

$$dBr(X) \cong H^1(X, \mathbb{Z}) \times \pi_0 \Gamma(X, B^2GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)).$$

□

Corollary 5.3. *All higher homotopical information of the smooth derived Brauer group is determined by the sheaf of grouplike spaces $GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)$. Equivalently, once the Postnikov tower of $GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X)$ is known, the smooth derived Brauer group is completely determined.*

6 Recovery of Classical Cohomological Invariants

Before discussing the classical consequences, we note that the arguments in this section are entirely sheaf-theoretic. Once Toën’s Brauer stack has been transported to the underlying simplicial commutative ring, the subsequent proofs depend only on the resulting unit sheaf $GL_1(\mathcal{O})$. Consequently, the same formal arguments apply equally to the sheaf of complex-valued smooth functions. This should not be interpreted as a theory of complex derived smooth manifolds, but merely as a comparison obtained by changing the coefficient sheaf.

Proposition 6.1 (Discrete structure sheaves). *Let (X, \mathcal{O}_X) be a derived smooth manifold whose structure sheaf is discrete. Then*

$$dBr(X) \cong H^1(X, \underline{\mathbb{Z}}) \times H^2(X, \mathcal{O}_X^\times).$$

Proof. If \mathcal{O}_X is discrete, then the derived unit sheaf is the ordinary sheaf of units:

$$GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X) = \mathcal{O}_X^\times.$$

Therefore

$$B^2GL_1(\mathcal{O}_X) \simeq B^2\mathcal{O}_X^\times \simeq K(\mathcal{O}_X^\times, 2).$$

By the standard identification of ordinary sheaf cohomology with maps into Eilenberg–MacLane objects in the ∞ -topos $\mathrm{Sh}(X, \mathcal{S})$ [Lurie-HTT, Remark 7.2.2.17],

$$\pi_0\Gamma(X, K(\mathcal{O}_X^\times, 2)) \cong H^2(X, \mathcal{O}_X^\times).$$

Combining this with Theorem 5.2 gives the result. \square

Corollary 6.2 (Ordinary smooth manifolds). *Let M be an ordinary paracompact smooth manifold, regarded as the derived smooth manifold (M, C_M^∞) . Then*

$$dBr(M) \cong H^1(M, \underline{\mathbb{Z}}) \times H^2(M, \underline{\mathbb{Z}}_2).$$

Proof. By Proposition 6.1,

$$dBr(M) \cong H^1(M, \underline{\mathbb{Z}}) \times H^2(M, (C_M^\infty)^\times).$$

It remains to compute the second factor. There is a short exact sequence of sheaves of abelian groups

$$1 \longrightarrow \{\pm 1\} \longrightarrow (C_M^\infty)^\times \longrightarrow (C_M^\infty)_{>0} \longrightarrow 1,$$

where the last map sends an invertible smooth function to its absolute value. The sheaf of positive smooth functions is isomorphic, by the logarithm, to the additive sheaf C_M^∞ . Since C_M^∞ is fine, hence soft, on a paracompact smooth manifold, its higher sheaf cohomology vanishes [Bredon, Chapter II]. The long exact cohomology sequence therefore gives

$$H^2(M, (C_M^\infty)^\times) \cong H^2(M, \{\pm 1\}) \cong H^2(M, \underline{\mathbb{Z}}_2).$$

This proves the formula. \square

Corollary 6.3 (Comparison with complex coefficients). *Although the intrinsic smooth structure sheaf in Spivak’s setting is real-valued, the same sheaf-theoretic computation applies after replacing C_M^∞ by the coefficient sheaf*

$$C_M^\infty(\mathbb{C})$$

of complex-valued smooth functions on an ordinary paracompact smooth manifold M . Let $dBr_{\mathbb{C}}(M)$ denote the pullback categorical Brauer group formed from this coefficient sheaf. Then

$$dBr_{\mathbb{C}}(M) \cong H^1(M, \underline{\mathbb{Z}}) \times H^3(M, \underline{\mathbb{Z}}).$$

Proof. By Proposition 6.1, applied to the discrete sheaf $C_M^\infty(\mathbb{C})$,

$$dBr_{\mathbb{C}}(M) \cong H^1(M, \underline{\mathbb{Z}}) \times H^2(M, C_M^\infty(\mathbb{C})^\times).$$

The exponential sequence of sheaves

$$0 \longrightarrow \underline{\mathbb{Z}} \longrightarrow C_M^\infty(\mathbb{C}) \xrightarrow{\exp(2\pi i -)} C_M^\infty(\mathbb{C})^\times \longrightarrow 1$$

is exact. Since $C_M^\infty(\mathbb{C})$ is a fine sheaf, its higher cohomology vanishes on a paracompact smooth manifold. The associated long exact sequence therefore gives

$$H^2(M, C_M^\infty(\mathbb{C})^\times) \cong H^3(M, \underline{\mathbb{Z}}).$$

This identifies the complex unit contribution with the usual Dixmier–Douady cohomology group. \square

Remark 6.4. *Corollary 6.2 uses real-valued smooth functions, whose units split into sign and positive parts and therefore produce the $H^2(M, \mathbb{Z}_2)$ term. Corollary 6.3 uses complex-valued smooth functions and recovers the Dixmier–Douady H^3 term through the exponential sequence. Thus the apparent discrepancy comes from the choice of real versus complex smooth coefficient sheaf, not from a failure of stackification.*

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